

The role of intuition in air traffic control decision-making

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>RESEARCH ARTICLE</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords: Air traffic management Aviation Decision making Human factor Intuitive decision making</p> <hr/> <p>Received: 22 September 2025 Revised: 28 October 2025 Accepted: 15 November 2025</p>	<p>The aim of the study was to examine the intuitive decision-making skills of air traffic controllers and determine whether these skills differ in terms of demographic variables. The study was conducted with the participation of 386 air traffic controllers. The data were collected using an intuitive decision-making scale and a demographic information form. The findings indicated that intuitive decision-making is a significant component in the decision-making processes of air traffic controllers ($M=3.4974$, $SD= 0.49564$). No significant differences were observed in the intuitive decision-making based on gender, experience, or the air traffic control unit. However, differences in intuitive decision-making skills were observed among controllers according to their educational background. This finding demonstrates that intuitive decision-making skills can be enhanced not only through experience but also through targeted learning investments. The study makes a significant contribution to the extant literature on the role of intuitive decision-making in air traffic management.</p>

1. Introduction

Aviation is a complex field that integrates advanced technology, regulatory frameworks, and human expertise to ensure the safety and efficiency of air travel (Harris & Stanton, 2010). With the continuous growth of global air traffic, aviation systems must evolve to accommodate increasing demands while maintaining high safety standards. Air traffic management plays a critical role in this process by mitigating imbalances between the demand for air traffic services and the capacity of the air transportation system, thereby ensuring the safe and efficient movement of aircraft within controlled airspace (Hoffman et al., 2010). A fundamental component of air traffic management is air traffic control, which relies on standardized procedures (Sanne, 2001), real-time problem-solving (Kuwata & Oohama, 1997), and technological support (Villiers, 1975) to maintain separation between aircraft and prevent conflicts.

Air traffic controllers manage air traffic across three distinct units, each responsible for different phases of flight: aerodrome control tower, approach control, and area control center. Air traffic controllers in the aerodrome control tower manage aircraft movements within the airport environment, directing takeoff, landing, and taxiing operations, ensuring the safe use of runways, and coordinating efficiently with pilots. Air traffic controllers in

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approach control manage aircraft during the arrival and departure phases, providing navigational assistance and sequencing instructions within terminal airspace to ensure smooth transitions between en-route flight and landing. Air traffic controllers in the area control center manage en-route aircraft traveling through controlled airspace at cruising altitudes, ensuring aircraft separation, coordinating with adjacent air traffic sectors, and optimizing flight routing to minimize delays. Each unit requires controllers to employ specialized decision-making strategies, particularly in high-traffic or emergency situations.

Human factors play a crucial role in air traffic control, as they directly influence controller performance (Hopkin, 2017). Particularly, cognitive (Niessen et al., 1999) and psychological processes (Wang et al., 2012) significantly affect operational efficiency and decision-making. The profession demands sustained attention, effective stress management, and rapid decision-making under pressure. Controllers must maintain a high level of situational awareness by continuously observing, interpreting, and predicting air traffic dynamics (Endsley & Rodgers, 1994; Niessen et al., 1999). Cognitive strategies assist controllers in managing workload and responding to unexpected events (Sperandio, 1971, 1978). Delays or errors in decision-making can lead to severe consequences, including aviation incidents and accidents (Anthony et al., 2023). The study conducted by D'Arcy and Rocco (2001) further emphasized that air traffic controllers prioritize safety, situational awareness, strategic planning, and contingency management as core aspects of their cognitive processes.

Decision-making plays a crucial role in air traffic control, as controllers must evaluate complex situations and choose the most appropriate course of action within limited time frames. It is a cognitive process that involves analyzing various options and selecting the most suitable one based on the available evidence and the demands of the situation (Chatoupis, 2007; Noone, 2002; Nutt, 1976). Early theories assumed that individuals were fully rational and always chose the best possible outcome. However, later research demonstrated that cognitive limitations often lead decision-makers to rely on heuristics or biased strategies, especially when faced with complex tasks (Brehmer, 1987; Cohen, 1993; Payne et al., 1988). More recent studies emphasize that decision-making consists of interconnected cognitive processes, including judgment formation, preference evaluation, and the integration of these evaluations into a final choice. These processes are influenced by systematic biases and practical constraints (Fischhoff & Broomell, 2020; Gonzalez & Meyer, 2016; Roth et al., 2021).

Decision-making is not a singular act but rather a habitual process shaped by past experiences and influenced by internal and external factors (Nas, 2010). Over time, individuals develop distinct decision-making styles that reflect their characteristic approach to evaluating and selecting alternatives. These styles are not innate but can be learned, refined, and developed through experience and education (Nutt, 1979). Instead of focusing only on selecting an option, decision-making style refers to the habitual and structured cognitive approach individuals use throughout the decision-making process (Connor & Becker, 2003). As an essential aspect of cognition, decision-making style affects how individuals process information and form judgments (Doktor & Hamilton, 1973).

Two primary paradigms in decision-making are rational and intuitive decision-making. Rational decision-making is characterized by systematic analysis, logical reasoning, and objective evaluation of alternatives (Evans et al., 1993; Scott & Bruce, 1995). This approach assumes that individuals gather and assess relevant information, consider risks and benefits, and make deliberate choices based on empirical evidence and structured logic. However, in many situations, individuals lack the time or resources for extensive analysis, making intuitive decision-making necessary. Intuitive decision-making allows individuals to make quick and effective choices by drawing on past experiences (Szanto, 2022), emotions, and previously acquired knowledge (Batchelor & Burch, 2013). In uncertain or time-constrained situations, decision-makers may not have the opportunity to engage in detailed analysis. In such cases, intuition helps them rapidly assess available information and select the most appropriate option (Dane & Pratt, 2007). Through experience, individuals recognize patterns and connections between events, enabling them to anticipate outcomes more efficiently (Salas et al., 2010). Intuitive decisions are often rooted in expertise and follow an implicit logical structure (Maldonato et al., 2018).

Both rational and intuitive decision-making approaches can be effective, particularly in dynamic and complex environments that require rapid and flexible solutions (Brusovansky et al., 2018). In the literature, decision-making processes are examined through intuitive and rational dimensions, and it is argued that these two systems can be distinguished from each other. Dual-process theories propose that the human mind contains an

evolutionarily older, automatic, and fast-operating intuitive system (System 1) and a newer, deliberate, slow, and analytical system (System 2) (Kahneman, 2011; Stanovich, 2009). System 1 mostly operates outside of conscious awareness, requires little cognitive effort, and is linked to emotional processes, whereas System 2 is engaged in situations requiring conscious attention, logical reasoning, and complex calculations. Kahneman (2011) emphasizes that System 1 “operates automatically and quickly, with little or no effort”, while System 2 can “construct thoughts in an orderly series of steps”. This perspective shows that intuitive processes function independently from analytical processes in the cognitive system. Similarly, Stanovich (2009) argues that two distinct systems govern the human mind: the first is associative, automatic, and fast, while the other is rule-based, controlled, and slow. This theoretical framework demonstrates that intuitive and rational decision-making processes are executed by different cognitive mechanisms and that each system has distinct goal orientations. Therefore, the literature supports the view that intuitive and rational decision-making processes operate through separate cognitive mechanisms and can be considered distinguishable.

The effectiveness of intuitive decision-making is enhanced by the ability to leverage accumulated knowledge, evaluate situational factors, and remain receptive to alternative solutions. Individuals who adopt this style often demonstrate confidence in the accuracy of their decisions (Can, 2009). Moreover, intuitive decision-makers are generally more adaptable to alternative courses of action, allowing them to respond more efficiently to unforeseen circumstances (Scott & Bruce, 1995). As intuitive decision-making develops through an extensive process involving experience, learning, factual knowledge, techniques, and cognitive frameworks, it has increasingly been acknowledged as a complementary approach to rational decision-making rather than an inferior alternative (Yaşar, 2016).

In the field of aviation, decision-making plays a particularly critical role in emergency situations, where rapid responses are essential under time constraints and high-pressure conditions (Kilic, 2024). Aviation emergencies may arise suddenly when a flight crew declares an emergency, or they may develop gradually over time (Malakis et al., 2010). These emergencies can range from relatively minor incidents that are easily manageable to highly complex situations that escalate unpredictably. While flight crews are primarily responsible for managing such emergencies, their ability to communicate and coordinate effectively with air traffic controllers significantly influences the overall outcome of the situation (Burian et al., 2005). Numerous aviation incidents in recent years have demonstrated that successful emergency management necessitates not only technical proficiency but also strong communication skills and collaborative decision-making between flight crews and air traffic controllers (Kara Arseven et al., 2025; Kilic, 2019; Kilic & Gumus, 2020; Kirwan et al., 2005)

Emergencies are an inherent aspect of aviation, requiring swift, well-coordinated, and accurate decision-making to maintain safety (Kilic, 2024). Throughout 2024, several high-profile aviation emergencies have emphasized the critical role of timely and precise decision-making in crisis management. On January 5, 2024, Alaska Airlines Flight 1282 experienced an explosive decompression due to a door plug failure on a Boeing 737 MAX 9, leading to an emergency landing in Portland, Oregon (McDermott, 2024). Similarly, on May 21, 2024, Singapore Airlines Flight 321 encountered severe turbulence over Myanmar, resulting in injuries to 144 individuals and one fatality, necessitating an emergency diversion to Bangkok (Ranter, 2025a). Engine failure and smoke in the cabin prompted Swiss International Air Lines Flight 1885 to execute an emergency landing in Graz, Austria, on December 23, 2024 (Ranter, 2025b). Just two days later, on December 25, 2024, Azerbaijan Airlines Flight 8243 suffered critical structural damage, reportedly due to a surface-to-air missile strike, declared an emergency, and subsequently crashed near Aktau, Kazakhstan, resulting in 38 fatalities (Trevelyan, 2025). A particularly catastrophic emergency occurred on December 29, 2024, when Jeju Air Flight 2216 suffered a bird strike followed by landing gear failure, leading to an emergency declaration and a crash after a runway overrun at Muan International Airport, causing 179 fatalities (Hradecky, 2024).

These incidents emphasize the unpredictable nature of aviation emergencies and the importance of rapid, informed, and effective decision-making in crisis management. The coordination between pilots and air traffic controllers, as well as the precise and timely exchange of critical information, played a decisive role in managing these crises. Such events further emphasize the significance of human factors, particularly the decision-making processes of air traffic controllers, in ensuring aviation safety. Given that emergencies often involve complex

and rapidly evolving dynamics, both analytical and intuitive decision-making approaches are essential for effective crisis response.

Hulderman (2003) states that the intuitive decision-making process involves cognitive flexibility, emotional awareness, and sensitivity to dynamic conditions. These abilities serve as crucial support mechanisms in decision-making, particularly for professionals such as air traffic controllers who operate in high-stress environments. Mendes et al. (2021) have shown that intuition plays a significant role in enabling individuals to make accurate and effective decisions in uncertain conditions. This finding explains why air traffic controllers frequently rely on intuitive decision-making when responding to emergencies. Shorrock and Kirwan (2002) emphasized that air traffic controllers' ability to make rapid decisions under stress is largely derived from accumulated experience and well-developed intuitive processes.

The intuitive decision-making abilities of air traffic controllers are critical in ensuring safety and mitigating operational risks, particularly in emergency scenarios characterized by severe time constraints. While traditional analytical decision-making processes rely on established procedures, emergency situations with rapidly changing conditions necessitate the effective use of intuitive decision-making mechanisms. In this regard, gaining a deeper understanding of how air traffic controllers employ intuitive decision-making and assessing the impact of these processes will contribute not only to individual performance enhancement but also to the broader sustainability of aviation safety. The aim of the study is to examine the intuitive decision-making skills of air traffic controllers and to determine whether these skills vary according to demographic factors, such as gender, education background, professional experience, and the specific air traffic control unit. Particular emphasis is placed on the role of professional experience in shaping these skills. The findings are expected to provide valuable insights into the significance of intuitive decision-making processes in the professional performance of air traffic controllers, thereby contributing to aviation safety and literature.

2. Methodology

The research examines the concept of intuitive decision-making in the context of air traffic control and focuses on the place of intuitive decision-making in professional practices. This study adopts a quantitative research design to systematically analyse relationships between variables through statistical methods. It will investigate how air traffic controllers are affected by experience, education, and other personal factors when dealing with critical situations. In addition, the main subject of the study is to examine the effect of demographic variables on intuitive decision-making. Air traffic controllers work in a constantly changing and complex work environment. In this environment, making fast and effective decisions is vital in ensuring flight safety. However, intuitive decision-making can be affected by individual factors. There is limited information in the literature on how gender, professional experience, education background, and the air traffic control unit they work in affect intuitive decision-making processes. This situation constitutes the main problem of the study.

RQ: To what extent do air traffic controllers' intuitive decision-making skills vary based on gender, education background, experience, and the air traffic control unit in which they are employed?

2.1. Data Collection Tools

2.1.1. Demographic Form

The demographic information form used in the study was prepared to determine the individual and professional characteristics of air traffic controllers. The form consists of four main categories to analyze the professional background and field of duty of the participants in detail: gender, education background, length of experience, and air traffic control unit. This information was used to evaluate the professional profiles of the participants in the study more comprehensively.

2.1.2. Decision-Making Styles Scale

The Decision-Making Styles Scale is a scale developed by Scott and Bruce (1995) and adapted to Turkish by Taşdelen (2002). The scale was designed to assess differences in individuals' decision-making styles and has a five-factor structure. Five items measuring the "intuitive decision-making" sub-dimension of this scale were used

in the study. The scale employs a 5-point Likert format. Scoring is as follows: "Strongly Disagree" (1), "Disagree" (2), "Neutral" (3), "Agree" (4), "Strongly Agree" (5).

2.2. Sample

The population of this study comprised air traffic controllers employed in Türkiye. The study employed a convenience sampling method, as participation was voluntary and based on the accessibility of licensed air traffic controllers working in operational units. Data were collected through an online survey, reaching a total of 386 participants. Given the demanding working conditions of air traffic controllers and their distribution across various locations in Türkiye, the online survey method was considered both practical and efficient. To enhance participation, the survey was disseminated via professional social media groups commonly used by air traffic controllers.

2.3. Data Analysis

The data obtained in the present study were analyzed using the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences, version 27.0 (SPSS 27.0). Initially, descriptive statistical analyses were conducted to summarize the demographic characteristics of the participants. To ensure the appropriateness of the data for further analyses, reliability analyses were performed to assess the internal consistency of the scales, and normality tests were conducted to examine whether the distribution of the data met the assumptions required for parametric testing. Subsequently, independent samples t-tests and one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) were carried out to explore potential differences between groups based on relevant demographic and occupational variables.

3. Results

A total of 386 air traffic controllers participated in the study and demographic information is shown in Table 1. 143 of the participants were female (37.0%) and 243 were male (63.0%). When the education background was examined, it was seen that the majority of the participants had a bachelor's degree (n = 317, 82.1%), while 69 participants (17.9%) had graduate education. When evaluated in terms of professional experience, 98 controllers (25.4%) had less than six years of experience, 58 (15.0%) had 6-10 years, 95 (24.6%) had 11-15 years, 53 (13.7%) had 16-20 years, and 82 (21.2%) had more than 20 years of experience. The participants were also classified according to the air traffic control unit they worked in. Accordingly, the majority of the participants worked in the aerodrome control unit (TWR) (n = 209, 54.1%). This is followed by those working in the approach control unit (APP) (n = 85, 22.0%) and those working in the area control center (ACC) (n = 92, 23.8%).

Table 1: Demographic Variables

Demographic Variables		N	%
Gender	Female	143	37.0
	Male	243	63.0
Education Background	Bachelor's degree	317	82.1
	Graduate degree	69	17.9
Experience (year)	< 6	98	25.4
	6-10	58	15.0
	11-15	95	24.6
	16-20	53	13.7
	> 20	82	21.2
Air Traffic Control Unit	Aerodrome Control Unit (TWR)	209	54.1
	Approach Control Unit (APP)	85	22.0
	Area Control Center (ACC)	92	23.8
Total		386	100

An analysis of the descriptive statistics for air traffic controllers' intuitive decision-making skills indicated that the mean score was 3.4974 (SD= 0.49564) as shown in Table 2, suggesting a high level of intuitive decision-making among participants. The skewness value of -0.160 and the kurtosis value of -0.326 indicate that the distribution exhibits a slightly platykurtic distribution, meaning it is somewhat flatter than a normal distribution. These skewness and kurtosis values suggest that the intuitive decision-making variable approximates a normal distribution, supporting the suitability of parametric analyses for further statistical examinations.

Table 2: Mean, Standard Error, and Normality Assessment of the Scale

		Statistic	Std.Dev.
Intuitive Decision-Making	Mean	3.4974	.49564
	Skewness	-.160	
	Kurtosis	-.326	

The reliability result for the intuitive decision-making scale is shown in Table 2. As shown in the table, the Cronbach’s alpha coefficient for the scale was .661. According to Özdamar (2016), Cronbach’s alpha coefficients below .40 indicate an unreliable scale, values between .40–.50 very low, .50–.60 low, .60–.70 acceptable, .70–.90 high, and values above .90 very high reliability. Based on this classification, the obtained value of .661 falls within the acceptable range, suggesting that the intuitive decision-making scale used in the study demonstrates an adequate level of internal consistency and is suitable for measuring the intended construct.

Table 3: Reliability Results

	Cronbach’s Alpha
Intuitive Decision-Making	0.661

To examine whether the intuitive decision-making skills of air traffic controllers differ according to gender, education background, professional experience, and the air traffic control unit they work in, independent samples t-test and one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) were applied.

The results of the independent samples t-test conducted according to the gender variable indicates that there is no significant difference in intuitive decision-making skills between female and male air traffic controllers ($t(384) = 0.142, p = .887$) as shown in Table 4. This finding suggests that intuitive decision-making skills are not significantly influenced by gender.

Table 4: Gender-Based Differences in Air Traffic Controllers' Intuitive Decision-Making

	Group	N	Mean	Std. Dev.	Std. Error	t	P
Gender	Female	143	3.5021	.47641	.03984	.142	.887
	Male	243	3.4947	.50756	.03256		

The independent samples t-test conducted in terms of education background indicates that there is a significant difference between air traffic controllers with a bachelor's degree and a graduate degree ($t(384) = -2.394, p = .017$), as shown in Table 5. This finding suggests that air traffic controllers with a graduate degree exhibit higher intuitive decision-making skills compared to those with a bachelor's degree.

Table 5: Education-Background Differences in Air Traffic Controllers' Intuitive Decision-Making

	Group	N	Mean	Std. Dev.	Std. Error	t	p
Education	Bachelor's degree	317	3.4694	.50086	.02813	-2.394	0.17
	Graduate degree	69	3.6261	.45233	.05445		

A one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) was applied to determine whether intuitive decision-making skills differ according to professional experience. The analysis results indicate that there is no significant difference between the groups ($F(4, 381) = 1.235, p = .295$), as shown in Table 6. This finding suggests that the length of experience does not have a significant impact on intuitive decision-making skills.

Table 6: Experience-Based Differences in Air Traffic Controllers' Intuitive Decision-Making

	Group	N	Mean	Std. Dev.	Std. Error	F	p
Experience (year)	< 6	98	3.5143	.49409	.04991	1.235	.295
	6-10	58	3.4103	.50600	.06644		
	11-15	95	3.5368	.49788	.05108		
	16-20	53	3.5774	.48144	.06613		
	> 20	82	3.4415	.49365	.05451		

A one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) was conducted to examine whether intuitive decision-making skills differ based on the air traffic control (ATC) unit in which controllers are employed. The results indicates no statistically significant difference in intuitive decision-making skills among controllers working in the aerodrome

control unit (TWR) ($M = 3.4900$, $SD = 0.49725$), approach control unit (APP) ($M = 3.5624$, $SD = 0.46547$), and area control center (ACC) ($M = 3.4543$, $SD = 0.51790$) ($F(2, 383) = 1.101$, $p = .334$), as shown in Table 7. This finding suggests that the operational unit in which air traffic controllers work does not have a significant impact on their intuitive decision-making skills.

Table 7: ATC Unit-Based Differences in Air Traffic Controllers' Intuitive Decision-Making

	Group	N	Mean	Std. Dev.	Std. Error	F	p
ATC Unit	TWR	209	3.4900	.49725	.03440	1.101	.334
	APP	85	3.5624	.46547	.05049		
	ACC	92	3.4543	.51790	.05400		

4. Discussion and Conclusion

In the study, the intuitive decision-making levels of air traffic controllers were examined and it was determined that this level was generally high. However, no significant difference was found between the intuitive decision-making levels according to demographic variables such as gender, ATC unit and professional experience. It was determined that there was only a statistically significant relationship between the education background and intuitive decision-making. These findings present important results when compared to similar studies in the literature.

The generally high level of intuitive decision making indicates that air traffic controllers effectively manage complex and rapid decision-making processes due to their duties. Air traffic control is a profession that requires rapid decision-making under high stress. Therefore, it is an expected result that air traffic controllers have advanced intuitive decision-making skills. It is stated in the literature that intuitive decision-making develops with experience and accelerates decision-making (Klein, 2017; Matzler et al., 2007). This finding of the study shows that air traffic controllers' intuitive approaches can produce faster and more effective solutions compared to analytical thinking, especially in emergency situations.

The study found that the intuitive decision-making levels of air traffic controllers did not show a significant difference according to gender, professional experience, and the ATC unit they were assigned to. This result suggests that intuitive decision-making is a job-oriented skill rather than an individual characteristic. Standard job descriptions and structured training processes for air traffic controllers contribute to each controller's development of these skills. Although it is stated in the literature that women are generally stereotyped as more intuitive and men as more rational decision-makers, studies on intuitive and analytical decision-making styles reveal contradictory results (Sadler-Smith, 2011). For example, in a study using emotion induction in a competitive environment, it was found that women made more intuitive decisions and men made more analytical decisions (Sinclair et al., 2010). However, some studies evaluating general decision-making styles have not found a significant difference between genders (Baiocco et al., 2009; Loo, 2000; Spicer & Sadler-Smith, 2005). Similarly, in the study, it was observed that gender did not have a decisive effect on intuitive decision-making skills. Similarly, studies examining the effect of experience on intuitive decision-making processes reveal that the tendency to make intuitive decisions strengthens with increasing experience (Pretz & Folse, 2011).

Intuitive decision-making allows individuals to recognize situations based on their level of knowledge and expertise (Klein, 2017). However, in the study, no significant relationship was found between experience and the level of intuitive decision-making. Various studies have shown that decision-making behaviors are affected not only by individual characteristics but also by the work environment and organizational factors. Şengöz (2021) emphasizes that decision-making processes are greatly affected by environmental factors. In this context, air traffic controllers' working environments supported by high-standard training programs, simulation applications, and structured operational procedures can support the development of intuitive decision-making skills regardless of experience level. It is recommended that intuitive decision-making processes be evaluated within the scope of professional competence and that training programs be structured accordingly.

The most notable finding of the study is the significant relationship between education background and intuitive decision-making. The results indicate that air traffic controllers with a graduate degree had higher levels of intuitive decision-making. This suggests that more advanced education improves individuals' intuitive thinking capacities, allowing them to make more effective decisions in complex situations. It is stated in the literature

that individuals with advanced education have more knowledge and that this knowledge strengthens intuitive processes (Hariri et al., 2014). Intuitive decision-making skills are not only an innate ability, but can also be developed through general experiences and specific learning efforts (Patton, 2003). In particular, the formation of habits and the acquisition of intuitive reactions to specific situations become possible through focused learning processes.

Despite all precautionary measures, accidents continue to occur in the aviation sector, and the number of serious accidents increased in 2024 compared to the previous year (International Civil Aviation Organization [ICAO], 2025). This situation once again emphasizes the impact of air traffic controllers' decision-making processes on safety. The fact that emergencies are unpredictable and require quick solutions by nature increases the importance of intuitive decision-making processes. Moreover, existing literature suggests that intuitive decision-making enables air traffic controllers to respond more swiftly and effectively in such situations (Mendes et al., 2021).

4.1. Implications and Limitations

The findings of the study are consistent with the literature that air traffic controllers' intuitive decision-making skills should be strengthened through training. Considering that air traffic management requires making high-risk decisions under time pressure, integrating structured simulation environments and experiential learning strategies into training programs can support controllers in making fast and effective decisions in complex situations (Gore et al., 2015; Salas et al., 2010). The study also highlights the potential role of graduate education in strengthening intuitive decision-making skills and suggests that advanced theoretical knowledge can improve cognitive processes under time pressure. From a practical perspective, aviation authorities and educational institutions should prioritize structured training modules aimed at improving air traffic controllers' intuitive decision-making competencies. In particular, the use of adaptive training methods that include dynamic simulations, scenario-based assessments, and continuous feedback mechanisms can strengthen controllers' ability to effectively manage unpredictable situations.

The limitations of the study include that the data was collected only cross-sectionally. Since cross-sectional studies are aimed at examining the current status of individuals, it is not possible to observe changes in individuals' decision-making skills over time. This situation provides a limited perspective in terms of understanding the development of intuitive decision-making skills. Future longitudinal studies should examine in more depth how air traffic controllers' decision-making processes change over time and how these processes can be improved with training. Another limitation is that the study was conducted only over a certain period of time. Intuitive decision-making is a dynamic process, and the conditions and training opportunities that air traffic controllers are exposed to may change over time. Therefore, different results may emerge when the study is repeated over a longer period of time. In addition, examining special training methods for the development of decision-making skills may contribute to the more effective strengthening of these skills.

This study provides important findings regarding the intuitive decision-making processes of air traffic controllers and reveals that these skills should be addressed as a part of the training processes. Since the ability of air traffic controllers to deal with emergencies is a factor that directly affects both safety and operational efficiency, further research into the development of these skills is important. Future studies could extend the current framework by linking intuitive decision-making to outcome variables such as job performance, fatigue, or workload to provide a more comprehensive understanding of its implications for operational safety and human performance. Exploring these relationships through longitudinal or experimental designs would further enrich the literature and contribute to evidence-based improvements in training and selection systems.

Conflicts of Interest

The authors declare that there is no conflict of interest regarding the publication of the paper.

Ethical approval

The study was approved for ethical suitability by the Ethics Committee of the International Science and Technology University with decision number 202502-01, issued during the meeting held on January 22, 2025.

References

- Anthony, S. W., Ahmad, R., & Osman, W. S. M. (2023). A Systematic Literature Review on Decision-Making Processes among Air Traffic Controllers (ATCOs) in Managing the Arrival of the Aircrafts during Conflict Resolution. *International Journal of Academic Research in Business and Social Sciences*, 13(8), 1465-1480. <http://dx.doi.org/10.6007/IJARBS/v13-i8/17623>
- Baiocco, R., Laghi, F., & D'Alessio, M. (2009). Decision-making style among adolescents: Relationship with sensation seeking and locus of control. *Journal of adolescence*, 32(4), 963-976. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.adolescence.2008.08.003>
- Batchelor, J. H., & Burch, G. F. (2013). Increasing Intuitive Decision Making Speed and Accuracy by Further Understanding Intuitive Decision Making Using Emotional Means. In *Developments in Business Simulation and Experiential Learning: Proceedings of the Annual ABSEL conference* (Vol. 40).
- Brehmer, B. (1987). The psychology of risk. In W. T. Singleton & J. Hovden (Eds.), *Risk and decisions* (pp. 25–39). John Wiley & Sons.
- Brusovansky, M., Glickman, M., & Usher, M. (2018). Fast and effective: Intuitive processes in complex decisions. *Psychonomic Bulletin & Review*, 25, 1542 - 1548. <https://doi.org/10.3758/s13423-018-1474-1>.
- Burian, B. K., Barshi, I., & Dismukes, K. (2005). The challenge of aviation emergency and abnormal situations (No. NASA/TM-2005-213462).
- Can, Ö. (2009). *Analysing the irrational beliefs and decision making styles of university students*. (Unpublished master's thesis). Selçuk University, Institute of Social Sciences, Konya, Türkiye.
- Chatoupis, C. (2007). Decision making in physical education: Theoretical perspectives. *Studies in Physical Culture & Tourism*, 14(2).
- Cohen, M. S. (1993). The naturalistic basis of decision biases. In G. Klein, J. Orasanu, R. Calderwood, & C. Zsombok (Eds.), *Decision making in action: Models and methods* (pp. 51–99). Ablex.
- Connor, P. E., & Becker, B. W. (2003). Personal value systems and decision-making styles of public managers. *Public Personnel Management*, 32(1), 155-180. <https://doi.org/10.1177/009102600303200109>
- Dane, E., & Pratt, M. (2007). Exploring Intuition and its Role in Managerial Decision Making. *Academy of Management Review*, 32, 33-54. <https://doi.org/10.5465/AMR.2007.23463682>.
- D'Arcy, J. F., & Della Rocco, P. S. (2001). *Air traffic control specialist decision making and strategic planning—a field survey* (No. DOT/FAA/CT-TN01/05).
- Doktor, R. H., & Hamilton, W. F. (1973). Cognitive style and the acceptance of management science recommendations. *Management science*, 19(8), 884-894. <https://doi.org/10.1287/mnsc.19.8.884>
- Endsley, M., & Rodgers, M. (1994). Situation Awareness Information Requirements Analysis for En Route Air Traffic Control. *Proceedings of the Human Factors and Ergonomics Society Annual Meeting*, 38, 71 - 75. <https://doi.org/10.1177/154193129403800113>
- Evans, J., Over, D., & Manktelow, K. (1993). Reasoning, decision making and rationality. *Cognition*, 49, 165-187. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0010-0277\(93\)90039-X](https://doi.org/10.1016/0010-0277(93)90039-X)
- Fischhoff, B., & Broomell, S. (2020). Judgment and decision making. *Annual Review of Psychology*, 71, 331–355. <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev-psych-010419-050747>
- Gonzalez, C., & Meyer, J. (2016). Integrating trends in decision-making research. *Journal of cognitive engineering and decision making*, 10(2), 120-122. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1555343416655256>
- Gore, J., Flin, R., Stanton, N., & Wong, B. L. (2015). Applications for naturalistic decision-making. *Journal of Occupational and Organizational Psychology*, 88(2). <https://doi.org/10.1111/joop.12121>
- Hariri, H., Monypenny, R., & Prideaux, M. (2014). Leadership styles and decision-making styles in an Indonesian school context. *School Leadership & Management*, 34(3), 284-298. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13632434.2013.849678>
- Harris, D., & Stanton, N. (2010). Aviation as a system of systems: Preface to the special issue of human factors in aviation. *Ergonomics*, 53, 145 - 148. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00140130903521587>
- Hoffman, J., DeVivo, R., & Mayo III, J. J. (2010). Separation Assurance in High-Density Airspace. *Encyclopedia of Aerospace Engineering*. <https://doi.org/10.1002/9780470686652.eae511>
- Hopkin, V. D. (2017). *Human factors in air traffic control*. CRC Press., London. <https://doi.org/10.1201/9780203751718>
- Hradecky, S. (2024). *Crash: Jeju B738 at Muan on Dec 29th 2024, gear up landing and overrun*. The Aviation Herald.
- Hulderman, M. A. (2003). *Decision-making styles and learning strategies of police officers: Implications for community policing*. Oklahoma State University.
- International Civil Aviation Organization (ICAO). (2025). *State of Global Aviation Safety*. https://www.icao.int/sites/default/files/sp-files/safety/Documents/ICAO_SR_2025.pdf
- Kahneman, D. (2011). *Thinking, fast and slow*. Farrar, Straus and Giroux.

- Kara Arseven, G., Ersin Öztopal, S. & Kılıç, B. (2025). Scenario-based learning to promote active learning among Airline Pilots. *Human Factors in Aviation and Aerospace*, 2, 27–36. <https://doi.org/10.26650/hfaa.2025>
- Kilic, B. (2019). HFACS Analysis for Investigating Human Errors in Flight Training Accidents. *Journal of Aviation*, 3(1), 28–37. <https://doi.org/10.30518/jav.553315>
- Kilic, B. (2024). *Aircraft Accident Investigation: Learning from Human and Organizational Factors* (3rd ed.). AmazonKDP. https://books.google.com.tr/books?hl=tr&lr=&id=iCEzEQAAQBAJ&oi=fnd&pg=PT29&ots=uUuXz0Gyp_&sig=-VP3YbRIMW0TSkneep-FfPsGBeo&redir_esc=y#v=onepage&q&f=false
- Kilic, B. & Gumus, E. (2020). Application of HFACS to the Nighttime Aviation Accidents and Incidents. *Journal of Aviation*, 4(2), 10–16. <https://doi.org/10.30518/jav.740590>
- Kirwan, B., Rodgers, M., Schafer, D. (2005). *Human Factors Impacts in Air Traffic Management*. Ashgate Publishing, Aldershot, UK.
- Klein, G. A. (2017). *Sources of power: How people make decisions*. MIT press.
- Kuwata, Y., & Oohama, H. (1997). A case study of a real-time problem solving strategy in an air traffic control problem. *Expert Systems with Applications*, 12(1), 71-79. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0957-4174\(96\)00081-4](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0957-4174(96)00081-4)
- Loo, R. (2000). A psychometric evaluation of the general decision-making style inventory. *Personality and individual differences*, 29(5), 895-905. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0191-8869\(99\)00241-X](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0191-8869(99)00241-X)
- Malakis, S., Kontogiannis, T., & Kirwan, B. (2010). Managing emergencies and abnormal situations in air traffic control (part I): Taskwork strategies. *Applied ergonomics*, 41(4), 620-627. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apergo.2009.12.019> [Get rights and content](#)
- Maldonato, M., Dell'Orco, S., & Sperandio, R. (2018). When intuitive decisions making, based on expertise, may deliver better results than a rational, deliberate approach. *Multidisciplinary approaches to neural computing*, 369-377. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-56904-8_35
- Matzler, K., Bailom, F., & Mooradian, T. A. (2007). Intuitive decision making. *MIT Sloan Management Review*, 49(1), 13.
- McDermott, J. (2024). *Explosive decompression reported on Alaska 737 MAX*. AirlineGeeks.
- Mendes, F., Mendes, E., Salleh, N., & Oivo, M. (2021). Insights on the relationship between decision-making style and personality in software engineering. *Information and Software Technology*, 136, 106586. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.infsof.2021.106586>
- Nas, S. (2010). Scientific Approaches To The Decision Making Styles. *Dokuz Eylul University Maritime Faculty Journal*, 2(2), 43-65.
- Niessen, C., Eyferth, K., & Bierwagen, T. (1999). Modelling cognitive processes of experienced air traffic controllers. *Ergonomics*, 42(11), 1507-1520. <https://doi.org/10.1080/001401399184857>
- Noone, J. (2002). Concept analysis of decision making. *Nursing Forum*, 37(3), 21–32. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1744-6198.2002.tb01007.x>
- Nutt, P. C. (1976). Models for decision making in organizations and some contextual variables which stipulate optimal use. *Academy of Management Review*, 1(2), 84–98. <https://doi.org/10.5465/amr.1976.4408670>
- Nutt, P. C. (1979). Influence of decision styles on use of decision models. *Technological Forecasting and Social Change*, 14(1), 77-93. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0040-1625\(79\)90058-1](https://doi.org/10.1016/0040-1625(79)90058-1)
- Özdamar, K. (2016). Eğitim, sağlık ve davranış bilimlerinde ölçek ve test geliştirme yapısal eşitlik modellemesi. *Eskişehir: Nisan*.
- Patton, J. R. (2003). Intuition in decisions. *Management decision*, 41(10), 989-996. <https://doi.org/10.1108/00251740310509517>
- Payne, J. W., Bettman, J. R., & Johnson, E. J. (1988). Adaptive strategy selection in decision making. *Journal of Experimental Psychology: Learning, Memory, and Cognition*, 14(3), 534–552. <https://doi.org/10.1037/0278-7393.14.3.534>
- Pretz, J. E., & Folse, V. N. (2011). Nursing experience and preference for intuition in decision making. *Journal of clinical nursing*, 20(19-20), 2878-2889. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2702.2011.03705.x>
- Ranter, H. (2025a). *Accident Boeing 777-31HER A6-EGU, Wednesday 14 March 2018*. <https://asn.flightsafety.org/>
- Ranter, H. (2025b). *Accident Airbus A220-300 HB-JCD, Monday 23 December 2024*. <https://asn.flightsafety.org/>
- Roth, E., Klein, D., & Ernst, K. (2021). Aviation decision making and situation awareness study: Decision making literature review. Contract Report USAARL-TECH-CR-2022-17. *Applied Decision Science, Cincinnati, OH, USA*.
- Sadler-Smith, E. (2011). The intuitive style: Relationships with local/global and verbal/visual styles, gender, and superstitious reasoning. *Learning and Individual Differences*, 21(3), 263-270. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.lindif.2010.11.013>
- Salas, E., Rosen, M. A., & DiazGranados, D. (2010). Expertise-based intuition and decision making in organizations. *Journal of management*, 36(4), 941-973. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0149206309350084>
- Sanne, J. (2001). Creating Safety in Air Traffic Control. *Administrative Science Quarterly*, 46, 345.
- Scott, S. G., & Bruce, R. A. (1995). Decision-making style: The development and assessment of a new measure. *Educational and psychological measurement*, 55(5), 818-831. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0013164495055005017>

- Shorrock, S. T., & Kirwan, B. (2002). Development and application of a human error identification tool for air traffic control. *Applied ergonomics*, 33(4), 319-336. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0003-6870\(02\)00010-8](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0003-6870(02)00010-8)
- Sinclair, M., Ashkanasy, N. M., & Chattopadhyay, P. (2010). Affective antecedents of intuitive decision making. *Journal of Management & Organization*, 16(3), 382-398. <https://doi.org/10.5172/jmo.16.3.382>
- Sperandio, J. C. (1971). Variation of operator's strategies and regulating effects on workload. *Ergonomics*, 14(5), 571-577.
- Sperandio, J. C. (1978). The regulation of working methods as a function of work-load among air traffic controllers. *Ergonomics*, 21(3), 195-202.
- Spicer, D. P., & Sadler-Smith, E. (2005). An examination of the general decision making style questionnaire in two UK samples. *Journal of Managerial Psychology*, 20(2), 137-149. <https://doi.org/10.1108/02683940510579777>
- Stanovich, K. E. (2009). Distinguishing the reflective, algorithmic, and autonomous minds: Is it time for a tri-process theory? In J. S. B. T. Evans & K. Frankish (Eds.), *In two minds: Dual processes and beyond* (pp. 55-87). Oxford University Press.
- Szanto, R. (2022). Intuitive decision-making and firm performance. *Journal of Decision Systems*, 31, 50 - 59. <https://doi.org/10.1080/12460125.2022.2080796>.
- Şengöz, M. (2021). A Phenomenological Evaluation On Decision-Making Behavior. *Takvim-i Vekayi*, 9(2), 115-132.
- Taşdelen, A. (2002). Decision making sytes of student teachers in relation to different psychosocial characteristics. (Unpublished doctoral dissertation). Dokuz Eylül University, Institute of Educational Sciences, İzmir, Türkiye.
- Trevelyan, M. (2025,). *Crashed Azerbaijani plane was riddled with holes after incident over Russia, report says*. Reuters.
- Villiers, J. (1975). The Automation of Air Traffic Control. *Journal of Navigation*, 28, 25-30. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0373463300025613>
- Wang, Y. Q., Wu, W. J., Liu, X. Y., & Xu, J. (2012). Analysis of Factors Influencing Air Traffic Controllers' Psychological Deviation under Emergency Condition. *Zhongguo Anquan Kexue Xuebao*, 22(9), 24-30.
- Yaşar, O. (2016). *Davranışsal Karar Verme, Düşünme, Problem Çözme*. Ankara: Detay Yayıncılık.

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